

ABOUT SULTAN ABU SAID MIRZA IN "BABURNAMA" INFORMATION

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Abstract : The article is in " Baburnoma ". Sultan Abu Said Mirza period to history about - his family tree , children , political activity , his in hand service did emirs and another data open to give directed .

Kalit so'zlar: Sulton Abu Said Mirzo, Ko'ragon, Temuriylar, Boburiylar, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, Boburnoma, Abdurazzoq Samarqandiy, Tarixi Rashidiy, Jahonshoh Qoraqo'yinli.

Amir Temur and The Timurids dynasty representatives not only central Asia , Iran and India maybe in history the world in history doesn't go out trace those who left This is a dynasty representatives this of regions different in the regions long period during rule those who did Movarounnahr , Khorasan , Iran and another in the regions power drove dynasty later on Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur political activity because of Afghanistan and North India in countries from new progressive find in history Great The Baburis dynasty name with enter took Actually Boburi mirzas their own dynasty Timurids or They were called Koragonians .

Of the dynasty immediately representatives between Sultan Abu Said Koragon [1] (1451-1469 rule did) separately place occupies Today's day thermoscience and philology the point in terms of this person history wide scale research reach main from tasks one is counted . Because in 1483 Ferghana in the valley In Aksida born and in 1530 death reached Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur To Sultan Abu Said Mirza grandson being his son Umarshaikh Mirza's is a child . It is known that in 1494 Umarshaikh mirza from his death 12 years later Babur Mr. M Ferghana to the throne sitting Accordingly , " Baburnama " by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur own

grandfather about gave information history science for extremely is important . In "Boburnoma" it is stated that Sultan Abu Said Mirza was the son of Sultan Mohammad Mirza, and he was the son of Mironshah Mirza, the third son of Amir Temur.

Although there is no information about the date of birth of Sultan Abu Said in historical sources, Abdurazzaq Samarqandi in his work "Matlai Sa'dayn wa Majbai Bahrain" in 1449 reports that the Sultan was 25 years old. Accordingly Sultan Abu Said Mirza in 1424 born information is given

The Timurids to the kingdom Sultan Abu Said is an adult reach period this Shah Rukh Mirza rule for years right will come Shah Rukh Mirza from his death and then the throne for struggles , Shahrukh Mirza descendants between late although - one how many yearly from struggles then in 1451 exactly Sultan Abu Said Mirza Movarounnahr throne for in struggles winner came

To Boburnoma according to The Timurids in the state internal from conflicts using , the ruler of Mongolia [2, 34-b] Esan Bugakhan Ferghana province Until Kandibodom come in Come to Andijan to the hand enters and population captive takes Historical In Rashidi of the khan walking Sayram , Turkestan and To Tashkent until continue this is it places completely destroyed back said that he returned info is given [3, 104- b] . These attacks until 1451 was Sultan Abusaid Mirza Samarkand throne to the hand after entering the country eastern borders defense to do for troop from , New from the city the next one In Isfara , Mongolia, Esan defeated Boga Khan .

This is the case In Boburnama as follows cited : "... of [Esan Bugakhon - FA] 's conspiracy once in a while Sultan Abusaid Mirza Yunus Khan this relationship I know , Abdulaziz Mirza olgon the owner Mrs take was , Iraq and You are happy wish weddings so , friends Boluk , Mongolian in ulus Khan by doing when sent Sagrichi district backs ok ul fursatta Esan Bugakhondin worse , to Mongolia come were , of these between came It's an opportunity Regards of the becks the eldest Sherhojibek

erdi , aning daughter Esan Davlatbegim took Mongolian net know hon and Esan Davlatbegim one white dress on top of it killer Khan raised [4, p. 67] . Through this The country of Sultan Abu Said eastern borders safety by providing attention Khurasan turned

It is known that the Timurids of the state Khurasan to the part this at the time Boysunkur of Mirza dead son Abulqasim Babur humble was His With Sultan Abu Said between surface came conflict in 1454 Abulqasim Babur by Samarkand siege to do with extremely increases .

Later, after the death of Abul Qasim Babur in 1457, he was able to occupy Khurasan and become the sole ruler of the Timurid kingdom. Another service of Sultan Abu Said to the history of Central Asia is that in 1457, using the internal struggles of the Timurid state, he recaptured Khurasan from Jahanshah, who captured Herat, and united the country. It is precisely because of these events that now the leadership of the Timurid family has passed into the hands of the descendants of Mironshah Mirza. This is it in turn of Sultan Abu Said Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur's grandfather as The Timurids of the dynasty in India big kingdom that's it is also special place of existence proof gives

In 1469, the death of Abu Said Mirza in a battle with white Turkmen caused the Timurid state to be administratively and territorially divided into two parts: Movarounnahr (Turkistan) and Khurason [5, 118- b] .

"Boburnoma" contains valuable information about Sultan Abusaid Mirza's family history going back to Amir Temur, as well as his children, sons who came to power - Sultan Ahmed Mirza, Sultan Mahmud Mirza, Omarshaikh Mirza. In particular, Sultan Abu Sa'id first gave Babur's father, Umarshaikh Mirza, the governorship of Kabul, and Babai Kabuli was appointed as his guardian. Mirza's circumcision wedding year because of Gorge From gas back to Samarkand brought Tuydan then , Temurbek big Umarshaikh To Mirza Ferghana province as given by

the Sultan Abusaid Mirza is also his son Umarshaikh To Mirza Andijan province God gave Give birth Temurtosh wait horse by doing sent , he writes Babur [2, p. 64] .

Also, in "Boburnoma" there is enough information about the begs and amirs who served during the reign of Sultan Abu Said Mirza. Among them Khudoyberdi Temurtash (emir), Ali Dost tagoyi (sagrychi district bek), Mir Ghiyos tagoyi, Ali Darvesh, Jonibek doldoy, Ahmed Hajibek, Pirmuhammad elchi Buga kavchin, Ayyub (It is extremely important because it provides detailed information about Sultan Abusaid's guardian), Mahmud Barlos, Muhammad Burunduq Barlos, Nuyonbek, Zunnun Arghun, Muhammad Sayyid Urus and other amirs [4].

Another piece of information is extremely interesting. In " Baburnoma". Hussein Boykara backs one by one when counting it's Alisher Navoi's turn comes : " Alisherbek again Navoi was , begi it's not was , maybe the interviewer was , when he was small school they are Feature great it is . Bilmon , what a fine know Sultan Abusaid mirza Hiridin excrement did Samarkand a went , how many yilkim , in Samarkand was ... ” [4, 233-b] .

In particular, Zahiriddin Babur's information about the Tarabkhana building in Herat is extremely interesting: "...The Tarabkhana was built in the middle of the garden. It is a smaller building. Two-story. But it is a nice building. They decorated the upper floor a lot. Four in the corner four has a room . That's four to the cell take entering home recreation is a room . It is a house of cells interval' i four shahnishin comfort was It's all over the house pictures put in This building Babur Mirza built although - but this images Sultan Abusaid Mirza ordered " [2, 145-b], saying information gives For us important , this information Sultan Abu Said Mirza not only state the ruler , perhaps He is also a lover of art from being information gives

VV Barthold own in "... Abu Sa'id his life style of work greatness , courage , and talent according to state leader as Babur , Akbar and Shah of the worlds worthy ancestor was ”[6, p. 69], as high price gives Own his opinion continue Abu Saeed Mirza rule years embroidery of the sect big representative Khoja Ahror's prestige

strengthened , with Sultan Abu Said Abdullah Mirza between Movarounnahr for in struggles Khoja Ahror's spiritual to help relied on emphasizes [6, 164-165-b] .

Turkish historian Y. Oztuna his own The Timurids dynasty to history dedicated in the work "... Abu Sa'id ibn Muhammad ibn Miron Shah ibn Temur , Temur's great-grandson and Baburshah's is the grandfather . He is from Timurids came out the most great of the rulers one , India Timurids (Baburis - AF) . grandfather Kingdom area : whole Iran , Afghanistan and Movarounnahrni own into cover received Sultan Abu Said Mirza Sultan With Fatih [7]. contemporary being the authority to the top one They came out in 1451 information gives [8, p. 31] .

In conclusion, among the representatives of the Timurid dynasty, Sultan Abu Said Mirza remained in history with the fact that his entire political activity was aimed at restoring the kingdom of Amir Timur. Also, he was the grandfather of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, and in our opinion, Babur Mirza's efforts to restore the Timurid state show that he is a worthy successor to his ancestor like Sultan Abu Said Koragon. From this point of view, the information related to the period of Sultan Abu Said Mirza in Babur Mirza's work "Baburnoma" is valuable for the fields of Temurology and Baburology.

Used literature list :

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3. Mirza Muhammad Haydar. Tarikh-i Rashidi / Introduction, translated from Persian by A. Urunbaev, R. P. Jalilova, L. M. Epifanova. Notes and indexes by R. P. Jalilova and L. M. Epifanova. – Tashkent: Fan, 1996. – 728 p.
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6. Barthold V.V. Ulugbek i ego vremya // Soch. t. II , ch. 2. - M.: 1964. - P.25-178.
7. Ottomans 1451-1481 referring to Sultan Mahmud II caught
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